

Original Article

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Prevalence and Knowledge of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease among Women of Childbearing Age in Narayi Community, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) is a major reproductive health problem associated with infertility, ectopic pregnancy, and chronic pelvic pain, particularly in low- and middle-income settings where sexually transmitted infections (STIs) remain prevalent. This study assessed the prevalence and level of knowledge of PID among women of childbearing age in Narayi community, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Methods: A community-based cross-sectional descriptive and analytical design was employed. Data were collected from 355 women aged 15–55 years using a structured questionnaire capturing socio-demographic characteristics, self-reported history of doctor-diagnosed PID, symptoms, knowledge, and selected risk factors. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were used for analysis at a 5% level of significance.

Results: The lifetime prevalence of self-reported doctor-diagnosed PID was 76.3% (95% CI: 71.6–80.4%), which may overestimate the true prevalence due to recall bias and diagnostic ambiguity. The most commonly reported symptoms were abnormal vaginal discharge (51.5%) and lower abdominal/pelvic pain (46.5%). Respondents demonstrated relatively high knowledge (mean score: 5.66 ± 0.94). PID diagnosis was significantly associated with age, history of STI treatment, miscarriage/abortion, vaginal douching, other infections, and condom use ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The findings highlight a high burden of self-reported PID and a gap between knowledge and preventive practices. Strengthening STI prevention, improving access to reproductive health services, and addressing behavioral risk factors are essential to reduce PID burden.

Keywords: Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID), Reproductive Health, Sexually Transmitted Infection, PID Burden

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Introduction

Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) is an infectious and inflammatory condition of the upper female genital tract, affecting structures such as the uterus, fallopian tubes, ovaries, and surrounding pelvic tissues [Jenkins & Vadakekut, 2025](#). In many settings, PID is clinically important because it is a major cause of preventable reproductive morbidity. PID commonly develops when microorganisms ascend from the lower genital tract to the upper genital tract. It is frequently associated with sexually trans-

mitted infections (STIs), especially *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, which are recognized globally as major drivers of PID and infertility [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023](#). The World Health Organization notes that gonorrhoea and chlamydia are major causes of PID and infertility in women, and that untreated chlamydia can result in PID and infertility [World Health Organization, 2025](#). The public health relevance of PID is closely tied to the global burden of STIs. It is estimated that more than one million curable STIs are acquired daily worldwide, with hun-

dreds of millions of new infections occurring annually [World Health Organization, 2025](#). Since many STIs are asymptomatic, infections may remain untreated and increase the risk of complications, including PID [World Health Organization, 2025](#).

PID has important short- and long-term consequences. Clinically, it may present with symptoms such as lower abdominal or pelvic pain, abnormal vaginal discharge, fever, dyspareunia, and abnormal bleeding; however, diagnosis can be challenging because symptoms vary and overlap with other gynecological conditions [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023](#). A major concern is that PID can lead to serious reproductive sequelae such as infertility, ectopic pregnancy, and chronic pelvic pain, particularly when diagnosis and treatment are delayed [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021](#).

Beyond infection exposure, multiple behavioral and contextual factors influence PID risk. One important behavioral factor discussed in the literature is vaginal douching. Evidence suggests that frequent douching is associated with increased risk of PID and other adverse reproductive outcomes [Zhang et al., 1997](#). Such practices may alter vaginal flora, facilitate ascending infection, and increase susceptibility to reproductive tract infections [Martino & Vermund, 2002](#).

Another critical issue is women's knowledge and awareness of PID, including its causes, symptoms, risk factors, prevention, and consequences. Knowledge is important because it influences health-seeking behavior, preventive practices, and early treatment decisions, such as timely STI treatment and partner management [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021](#). Studies in Nigeria indicate that awareness and preventive practices related to PID vary across populations and may be influenced by media exposure and socio-demographic context [Njoku & Anorue, 2021](#).

Although PID is a well-recognized clinical and public health problem, prevalence estimates vary widely across settings due to differences in diagnostic criteria, population characteristics, healthcare access, and study design. For instance, in the United States, the prevalence of self-reported lifetime PID among sexually experienced women aged 18–44 years was estimated at 4.4% [Kreisel et al., 2017](#). In contrast, Nigerian facility-based stud-

ies often report higher proportions among women attending gynecology clinics or presenting with pelvic complaints, reflecting differences in study populations and case ascertainment [Howells & Emmanuel, 2018](#). These variations highlight the need for context-specific evidence on PID prevalence and knowledge among women of reproductive age in local communities, including Narayi community in Kaduna State.

This study was therefore conducted to determine the prevalence and level of knowledge of pelvic inflammatory disease among women of childbearing age in Narayi community, Kaduna State, and to examine associated socio-demographic, reproductive, and behavioral factors.

Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in Narayi community, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Narayi is a residential community located within Kaduna metropolis, comprising a mix of socio-economic groups and women of varying educational, marital, and occupational backgrounds.

Study Design

This study employed a community-based cross-sectional descriptive and analytical design.

Study Population

The study population consisted of women of childbearing age residing in Narayi community. Women of childbearing age were defined as those within the reproductive age bracket of 15–55 years, consistent with reproductive health research standards [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021](#).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Women aged 15–55 years
- Residents of Narayi community for at least 6 months
- Willing to provide informed consent
- Able to understand and respond to the questionnaire

Exclusion criteria:

- Women outside the specified age range
- Visitors or non-residents
- Women who declined participation
- Women too ill to participate at the time of data collection

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was calculated using the single population proportion formula for prevalence studies:

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times p \times q}{d^2}$$

where n is the required sample size, z is the z -score at 95% confidence level (1.96), p is the estimated prevalence, $q = 1 - p$, and d is the desired precision (0.05).

The prevalence estimate ($p = 0.75$) was obtained from a Nigerian study conducted among women attending a gynecology clinic [Iwu et al., 2024](#). Substituting into the formula yielded $n = 288.12$, approximated to 288.

To account for non-response, a 10% adjustment was applied:

$$n_{\text{adjusted}} = \frac{n}{1 - 0.10} = 320$$

A total of 355 respondents were included in the final analysis, exceeding the minimum required sample size.

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was used. First, Narayi community was divided into identifiable residential clusters. Second, households within selected clusters were approached systematically. Third, where more than one eligible woman was present in a household, one respondent was selected randomly to minimize clustering bias.

However, elements of convenience sampling were present due to accessibility and willingness of respondents, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured, electronically administered questionnaire adapted from a

similar study [Iwu et al., 2024](#). The questionnaire was administered via Google Forms.

The instrument comprised four sections:

1. Socio-demographic characteristics
2. PID history and symptoms
3. Knowledge of PID
4. Risk factors for PID

Knowledge items were scored as follows: correct responses = 1, incorrect or “don’t know” responses = 0, yielding a total score ranging from 0 to 7.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The instrument was reviewed by public health experts and supervisors for clarity and relevance. A pilot test was conducted among women in a similar community outside Narayi.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

Data were entered, cleaned, and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize variables, including frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and mean and standard deviation for continuous variables. The prevalence of self-reported doctor-diagnosed PID was estimated with 95% confidence intervals.

Knowledge scores were categorized as:

- Good knowledge: scores ≥ 5
- Poor knowledge: scores < 5

Bivariate analysis was conducted using Pearson’s Chi-square (χ^2) test to assess associations between PID diagnosis and selected variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Missing data were handled using available case analysis, resulting in slight variations in denominators.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional ethics review committee. Informed consent was obtained prior to participation. Participation was voluntary, confidentiality was maintained, and no identifying information was included in the analysis. Respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any time. Sensitive questions were handled respectfully to minimize discomfort.

Limitations

The study had some limitations. It relied on self-reported PID diagnosis, which may introduce reporting bias. The cross-sectional design limits causal inference, and recall bias may affect the accuracy of responses. Additionally, social desirability bias may have influenced reporting of sensitive behaviors.

Results

Data from 355 respondents were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) and Chi-square tests for association. All statistical analyses were conducted at a 5% level of significance.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

A total of 355 questionnaires were analyzed. Respondents' ages ranged from 15 to 55 years, with a mean age of 34.36 ± 9.87 years ($n = 352$), indicating that the sample population was largely within the mid-reproductive age group.

Most respondents were married (193/354), followed by single (123/354), while widowed (23/354) and divorced (15/354) constituted smaller proportions. The predominance of married respondents (54.5%) suggests a largely sexually active adult population.

Regarding educational attainment, the majority of respondents (56.7%; 200/353) had secondary education, followed by tertiary (117/353) and primary education (36/353). The sample was predominantly Christian (93.5%). For analytical purposes, age was categorized into four groups.

Prevalence of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID)

The lifetime prevalence of PID based on self-reported history of doctor diagnosis was 76.3% (270/354). The estimated prevalence was 76.3% with a 95% confidence interval of 71.6% to 80.4%.

Current symptoms reported by respondents included unusual vaginal discharge (51.5%), lower abdominal or pelvic pain (46.5%), fever or chills (38.9%), burning sensation during urination (34.1%), bleeding between periods or after intercourse (32.7%), and pain during sexual intercourse

(32.4%). Multiple symptoms could be reported by the same respondent. Unusual vaginal discharge was the most commonly reported symptom, followed by pelvic pain.

This estimate is based on self-reported doctor diagnosis and may overestimate the true prevalence due to recall bias and diagnostic ambiguity.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents ($n = 355$)

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
15–24	79	22.4
25–34	89	25.3
35–44	118	33.5
45–55	66	18.8
Marital Status		
Single	123	34.7
Married	193	54.5
Divorced	15	4.2
Widowed	23	6.5
Educational Level		
Primary	36	10.2
Secondary	200	56.7
Tertiary	117	33.1
Occupation		
Student	95	26.8
Business/Trading	87	24.5
Self-employed	54	15.2
Other	43	12.1
Farming	29	8.2
Civil servant	28	7.9
Teaching	19	5.4
Religion		
Christianity	332	93.5
Islam	22	6.2
Other	1	0.3

Percentages may not sum to 100 due to rounding.

Knowledge of PID

Knowledge was assessed using seven statements on PID, scored as 1 for correct responses and 0 for incorrect or "don't know" responses, yielding a total score ranging from 0 to 7. Respondents demonstrated generally high knowledge, with a mean score of 5.66 ± 0.94 and a median score of 6.

Based on the defined cut-off, the majority of respondents demonstrated good knowledge of PID,

indicating relatively high awareness of its causes, symptoms, and prevention.

Table 2: Prevalence of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease and Reported Symptoms

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
PID Diagnosis		
Yes	270	76.3
No	84	23.7
Current Symptoms		
Unusual vaginal discharge (color/odor)	183	51.5
Lower abdominal/pelvic pain	165	46.5
Fever or chills	138	38.9
Burning on urination	121	34.1
Bleeding between periods or after intercourse	116	32.7
Pain during sexual intercourse (dyspareunia)	115	32.4

Multiple responses were allowed for symptoms; percentages may exceed 100%.

Association Between PID and Socio-Demographic and Behavioral Factors

Chi-square tests were used to assess associations between PID diagnosis and selected variables.

PID prevalence differed significantly across age groups, increasing from 51.9% among respondents aged 15–24 years to 89.8% among those aged 35–44 years ($p < 0.001$). A significant association was also observed between PID diagnosis and history of STI treatment ($p < 0.001$), miscarriage or induced abortion ($p < 0.001$), frequent vaginal douching ($p < 0.001$), history of urinary or genital infections other than STIs ($p < 0.001$), and condom use frequency ($p < 0.01$).

Married and widowed women had higher PID prevalence compared to single and divorced respondents. No statistically significant association was observed between educational attainment and PID diagnosis. Similarly, no significant associations were found for age at first sexual intercourse before 18 years ($p = 0.073$), having multiple sexual partners in the past year ($p = 0.966$), or intrauterine

device (IUD) use ($p = 0.830$).

Table 3: Association between PID Diagnosis and Selected Variables

Variables	PID Yes n (%)	χ^2 (df)	p-value
Age group			
15–24	41 (51.9)	39.91 (3)	<0.001
25–34	66 (75.0)		
35–44	106 (89.8)		
45–55	55 (83.3)		
STI treatment			
No	72 (61.5)	38.33 (1)	<0.001
Yes	216 (91.9)		
Abortion/miscarriage			
No	185 (69.8)	16.37 (1)	<0.001
Yes	83 (90.2)		
Douching			
No	91 (63.6)	16.43 (1)	<0.001
Yes	180 (84.5)		
Other infection			
No	55 (61.1)	13.25 (1)	<0.001
Yes	217 (81.6)		
Condom use			
Always	34 (58.6)	10.04 (2)	0.007
Sometimes	152 (83.1)		
Never	86 (75.4)		

Note: Pearson’s chi-square test was used. Percentages are row percentages. PID = Pelvic Inflammatory Disease.

Discussion

This study found a high lifetime prevalence of self-reported doctor-diagnosed pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) (76.3%) among women of child-bearing age in Narayi community. While this suggests a substantial reproductive health burden, the estimate should be interpreted with caution. The reliance on self-reported diagnosis introduces potential recall bias, misclassification, and diagnostic ambiguity. PID is often diagnosed clinically without definitive laboratory confirmation, and its symptoms overlap with other reproductive tract infections, which may lead to over-reporting in community-based surveys

Table 4: Association between PID Diagnosis and Selected Factors

Variables	Freq (n)	PID n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Age group			39.91	0.001
15–24	79	41 (51.9)		
25–34	88	66 (75.0)		
35–44	118	106 (89.8)		
45–55	66	55 (83.3)		
Marital status			28.42	0.001
Single	122	76 (62.3)		
Married	193	164 (85.0)		
Divorced	15	8 (53.3)		
Widowed	23	21 (91.3)		
Education			0.89	0.640
Primary	36	28 (77.8)		
Secondary	200	149 (74.5)		
Tertiary	116	91 (78.4)		
STI treated			38.33	0.001
No	117	72 (61.5)		
Yes	235	216 (91.9)		
Abortion/miscarriage			16.37	0.001
No	265	185 (69.8)		
Yes	92	83 (90.2)		
Douching			16.43	0.001
No	143	91 (63.6)		
Yes	213	180 (84.5)		
Other infection			13.25	0.001
No	90	55 (61.1)		
Yes	266	217 (81.6)		
Pelvic procedure			1.47	0.226
No	306	231 (75.5)		
Yes	49	41 (83.7)		
Condom use			10.04	0.007
Always	58	34 (58.6)		
Sometimes	183	152 (83.1)		
Never	114	86 (75.4)		
First sex before 18			3.21	0.073
No	215	155 (72.1)		
Yes	140	115 (82.1)		
Multiple partners			0.00	0.966
No	58	44 (75.9)		
Yes	297	226 (76.1)		
IUD use			0.05	0.830
No	332	253 (76.2)		
Yes	23	18 (78.3)		

Note: Pearson's chi-square test was used. Percentages are row percentages. PID = Pelvic Inflammatory Disease; IUD = Intrauterine Device.

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023; Jenkins & Vadakekut, 2025. Therefore, the reported prevalence likely overestimates the true burden. Compared with international population-based evidence, this estimate is considerably higher. For example, a study using NHANES data in the United States reported a lifetime PID prevalence of 4.4% among sexually experienced women Kreisel et al., 2017. This disparity may reflect differences in healthcare systems, STI control programs, diagnostic practices, and study design. In contrast, higher prevalence estimates have been reported in facility-based Nigerian studies, particularly among women presenting with gynecological complaints Howells & Emmanuel, 2018; Iwu et al., 2024, highlighting the influence of study setting and case definition.

The most commonly reported symptoms in this study—abnormal vaginal discharge and lower abdominal or pelvic pain—are consistent with established clinical presentations of PID. According to existing evidence, PID commonly presents with pelvic pain, abnormal discharge, and other non-specific symptoms, and diagnosis is often based on clinical findings rather than laboratory confirmation Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023. Clinical summaries also emphasize that PID symptoms may overlap with other gynecological conditions, limiting diagnostic specificity Jenkins & Vadakekut, 2025. Therefore, while the symptom profile supports the plausibility of reproductive tract infections, it does not confirm PID diagnosis.

Increasing age was significantly associated with PID diagnosis in this study. This may reflect cumulative exposure to risk factors over the reproductive lifespan, as older women have had more years of potential exposure to sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and reproductive health events. Similar patterns have been reported in epidemiological studies of reproductive tract infections Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021.

History of STI treatment was also strongly associated with PID. This finding is consistent with established evidence that untreated or recurrent STIs, particularly *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, can ascend to the upper genital tract and result in PID Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023; World Health Organization,

2025. Effective STI prevention, early diagnosis, and partner treatment are therefore critical in reducing PID burden.

Vaginal douching was significantly associated with PID in this study. This aligns with existing literature demonstrating that douching disrupts normal vaginal flora and facilitates ascending infection, thereby increasing the risk of PID [Martino & Vermund, 2002](#); [Scholes et al., 1993](#); [Zhang et al., 1997](#). Public health messaging should therefore discourage this practice.

History of miscarriage or induced abortion was also associated with PID. This may reflect increased vulnerability to infection due to complications or post-procedure infections, particularly in settings with limited access to safe reproductive health services. However, given the cross-sectional design, these associations should be interpreted cautiously.

Respondents demonstrated relatively high knowledge of PID, with a mean score of 5.66 out of 7. This suggests a reasonable level of awareness regarding PID causes, symptoms, and prevention. However, the persistence of high PID prevalence despite good knowledge indicates a potential knowledge-behavior gap. Similar findings have been reported in other Nigerian studies, where awareness does not necessarily translate into preventive practices due to structural and socio-cultural barriers [Njoku & Anorue, 2021](#).

Knowledge alone may be insufficient to reduce PID burden in the absence of enabling factors such as access to healthcare, affordability of services, and supportive social environments. Additionally, because the outcome measure was lifetime diagnosis, it is possible that some respondents acquired knowledge after experiencing PID, further complicating interpretation.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, PID diagnosis was based on self-reported doctor diagnosis, which may be subject to recall bias, misclassification, and diagnostic ambiguity, potentially leading to overestimation of prevalence. Second, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causality between variables. Third, elements of convenience sampling may limit the generaliz-

ability of findings. Additionally, sensitive variables such as sexual behavior may be affected by social desirability bias.

Conclusion

This study identified a high prevalence of self-reported doctor-diagnosed pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) among women of childbearing age in Narayi community. While this suggests a significant reproductive health burden, the estimate should be interpreted cautiously due to reliance on self-reported diagnosis. Respondents demonstrated relatively high knowledge of PID; however, the persistence of high prevalence indicates a gap between knowledge and preventive practices. Strengthening STI prevention, improving access to reproductive health services, and addressing behavioral risk factors are critical to reducing the burden of PID in the community.

Implications for Practice and Policy

The findings of this study highlight the need for comprehensive reproductive health interventions in Narayi community. Strengthening STI prevention and early treatment is essential, given the established link between sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and PID [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021](#); [World Health Organization, 2025](#). Public health interventions should also address harmful practices such as vaginal douching, which has been consistently associated with increased PID risk [Zhang et al., 1997](#).

Improving access to youth-friendly and women-centered reproductive health services is critical to facilitate early diagnosis and treatment. In addition, integrating PID education into community and maternal health programs may enhance awareness while addressing structural barriers that limit behavior change. Overall, reducing PID burden in the community will require a combination of behavioral, clinical, and health system interventions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several priority actions are recommended to reduce the burden of pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) in Narayi community. Strengthening STI prevention and early

treatment services should be prioritized, particularly through routine risk assessment, timely diagnosis, and partner management within primary healthcare settings. Targeted community health education should focus on discouraging harmful practices such as vaginal douching and promoting early health-seeking behavior for reproductive tract symptoms. Improving access to youth-friendly and women-centered reproductive health services is essential to ensure confidentiality, affordability, and timely care. Integration of PID education into maternal and community health programs should be strengthened to sustain awareness and promote preventive practices. Further research using clinically or laboratory-confirmed diagnosis is recommended to provide more accurate estimates of PID burden.

What is Known About This Topic

Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) is a significant cause of reproductive morbidity, particularly in low- and middle-income settings. It is commonly associated with untreated sexually transmitted infections and may lead to infertility, ectopic pregnancy, and chronic pelvic pain. Awareness and pre-

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ventive practices vary across populations, and gaps often exist between knowledge and behavior.

Authors' Contributions

Saifullah Mukadam Abdulhamid conceptualized the study, designed the methodology, supervised data collection, performed data analysis and interpretation, and drafted the manuscript. Aliyu Simon contributed to data collection and assisted in manuscript drafting. Bashir Saidu Tal, Jamila Muhammad Wada, Nazifa Abdullahi Abdullahi, and Emi Morrison Abdulaziz contributed to manuscript review and revision. Yusuf Yakubu Arrigasiyyu and Amadaoui William Forsman contributed to the critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in respect of this study

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